

BOOK REVIEW**Velislava Chavdarova****“St. Cyril and St. Methodius” University of Veliko Tarnovo, Bulgaria**
[v_chavdarova@mail.bg]**Revealing the Unseen: Stoil Mavrodiev's Exploration of the Psychoanalytical Contributions of Lyubomir Rusev**

Abstract: *The review of the book "The Psychoanalytic Work of Lyubomir Rusev" presents a theoretical study carried out by Stoil Mavrodiev, dedicated to the description of the psychoanalytic work of Lyubomir Rusev Minchev, until recently unknown to both the scientific community and the general public, in which the author substantiates his original contribution to the methodology of this paradigm. The book provides an analytical and interpretive, critical reading of Lyubomir Rusev's work and his contribution to Bulgarian science, literary studies, pedagogical practice, and more.*

Keywords: *history of psychology; Bulgaria; psychoanalysis; methodology.*

Mavrodiev, Stoil (2021) *The psychoanalytic work of Lyubomir Rusev*. Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria: University Publishing House “Neofit Rilski”; p. 139. ISBN 978-954-00-0251-4.

In his monograph "The Psychoanalytic Work of Lyubomir Rusev", Stoil Mavrodiev presents both a philosophical-analytical and an empathically verified analysis of the psychoanalytic work of Lyubomir Rusev Minchev who was until recently unknown to both the scientific community and the general public. "The main reason is that the works of the intellectuals who professed Remkeanism and

other ideological philosophical doctrines were banned after 1944 by the communist government established in Bulgaria" /p. 2/.

The author has developed his exposition in a total volume of 139 pages, having successfully achieved the intended goal of exploring the entire psychoanalytic oeuvre of Lyubomir Rusev Minchev, revealing his main ideas and contributions to Bulgarian science, literary studies, and pedagogical practice. I consider the completed volume to be exemplary within the scientific genre. The text is both readable and engaging, and skillfully directs the reader towards a neglected and unexplored psychoanalytic perspective that has marked Bulgarian psychological historiography to date.

I must express my admiration for the author's efforts in identifying, locating and accessing relevant sources. Mavrodiev has successfully built on his own scholarly achievements related to the rehabilitation of Bulgarian psychoanalysts' place in contemporary philosophical, psychological and dialectical discourse. The presented work is a part of a commendable scientific journey systematizing, conceptualizing and summarizing knowledge about the most intensive period in the development of the psychoanalytic movement in Bulgaria. It rehabilitates the movement's place in the system of psychological knowledge and demonstrate the original contribution of Bulgarian psychologists to the methodology of this paradigm. The reviewed monograph is immanently linked to the book "Psychoanalysis in Bulgaria until the 1940s", in which the author offers an analytical-interpretive, critical reading of the work of Bulgarian psychoanalytically oriented authors and their contributions to pedagogy, sociology, philosophy, religion, literary studies, and more.

Mavrodiev's original, creative and erudite scientific analysis employs content analysis, interpretation of original texts, the biographical method and the comparative logical method, aiming to rethink some fundamental principles and concepts by identifying their heuristic potential and application in psychology, philosophy, pedagogy, philology, religion, medical and legal practice.

The theoretical basis of the work is extremely informative and convincingly introduces us to the scientific work of Lyubomir Rusev. Rusev's work is conventionally divided into several categories: pedagogical works, including articles devoted to education; fundamental issues of psychoanalysis; psychoanalysis of artistic creativity; and psychoanalysis of religion and social phenomena /p. 3/.

Guided by the belief that the scientific work of Lyubomir Rusev should be rehabilitated and professionally studied, the author has dili-

gently located and studied Rusev's key writings. Stoil Mavrodiev successfully demonstrates that the works of Lyubomir Rusev have not lost their relevance and would enrich the knowledge of psychologists, pedagogues, philosophers, philologists and other specialists. I believe that such a manner of scholarly writing – especially of a historical nature – demonstrates one of the most valuable qualities of any researcher: scholarly conscientiousness.

The introductory text /pp. 2-3/, with its unmistakable philosophical emphasis, convincingly reveals the motivation for choosing this particular author and topic in the history of the Bulgarian psychological tradition, and accurately highlights the key aspects of the research design.

The author clearly adheres to the view that knowledge of the past in the development of a science aids a more authentic understanding of the present and a more accurate prediction of its future. In this context, the thesis is put forward that "our authors have also made their own original contributions to psychoanalysis. Ivan G. Kinkel developed the question of the origin of religion, and his study "Towards the Question of the Psychological Foundations and Origin of Religion" (Sofia, 1921) was published in the international psychoanalytic journal "Imago" (published in the period 1912 – 1937 in Vienna and Leipzig), receiving admiration by Sigmund Freud himself and his assistant Otto Rank. Lyubomir Rusev's approach is original, exploring the interrelationship between hunger and libido; he applies the psychoanalytic method to the artistic work of Hristo Botev, Peyo Yavorov and others" /p. 2/.

Stoil Mavrodiev's research efforts are focused on deepening the knowledge of national traditions in the development of Bulgarian psychology and its psychoanalytic perspective, highlighting the unique contributions of analysts up to the 1940s and beyond. His work seeks to identify the original contributions of Lyubomir Rusev, challenging the conventional view of Rusev's activity merely as a popularizer of Freud's ideas by undertaking a kind of rehabilitation of his place in the history of Bulgarian psychology. I highly appreciate the creativity of this approach, which I find successfully realized in the book.

In the first part of the monograph /pp. 9-15/, Lyubomir Rusev's life and key works, part of his scientific heritage, are presented. "The scientific work of Lyubomir Rusev can be divided into three main thematic areas: pedagogical themes, social-psychological and psychoanalytical research. The main scientific interests of the first half of his life were in the field of psychoanalysis. His books and articles are devoted not only to popularizing this doctrine, but also to applying it as the primary method-

ology for interpreting the literary works of Botev and Yavorov, Slaveikov (father and son), and others; he was interested in education and the formation of personality, as well as the depths of human culture and religion" /p. 4/.

Within the well-defined parameters of this conceptual framework, Mavrodiev skillfully directs attention to the activities of creating a "Pedagogical Dictionary", which explains over a thousand basic pedagogical concepts and contains biographical data on Bulgarian and foreign pedagogues. Such concepts as "abstraction", "automatism", "apperception", "associative experiment", "association" are clarified based on the views of Wilhelm Maximilian Wundt (August 16, 1832 – August 31, 1920). The notion of "education" is discussed thoroughly, presenting quotations of eminent philosophers on problems of education, and differentiating between the theory and practice of education, among other topics.

The following chapters present in a coherent sequence the philosophy and methodology of Lyubomir Rusev's psychoanalytic readings in various problem areas: pedagogy, developmental psychology, psychohygiene and psychoprophylaxis, social phenomena, education and personality formation, the relation of psychoanalysis to fiction, and more.

The inclusion of Stoil Mavrodiev's own interpretation of Lyubomir Rusev's psychoanalysis of Botev's and Yavor's works in the structure of the exposition also deserves positive evaluation. The author demonstrates self-confidence as a researcher and the ability to think independently in the final main chapter, entitled "The Polemic between Lyubomir Rusev and Mikhail Dimitrov". Here, the interpretive framework correctly and thoroughly presents the key ideas of their counter-argument, addressing both the methodology of psychoanalysis and its application to various fields of knowledge and culture.

A number of noteworthy contributions can be identified in this monographic study. The fact that the period between the 1920s and the 1940s remains unsystematically studied in our psychological historiography gives me a strong reason to argue that as a researcher Stoil Mavrodiev stands out as an innovator who consistently and thoroughly set the general direction for research in the Bulgarian history of psychology, which he further deepened through an analytical and interpretive reading of the works of prominent figures such as Lyubomir Rusev.

The absence of systematic analytical studies on the intensive period of the psychoanalytic movement in Bulgaria, and the rehabilitation of its place in psychological knowledge, highlights Mavrodiev's significant contribution. He demonstrates that Lyubomir Rusev's original contribu-

tions to the methodology of psychoanalysis have broader implications for the evolution of psychological ideas both nationally and internationally.

The exposition is original, well-conceived and built into a logically developed presentation of themes that have captivated Lyubomir Rusev and other psychoanalytically oriented intellectuals who sought explanations of universal, behavioral and personal problems in the socio-cultural context of their respective historical times. Their foundational ideas go far beyond the boundaries of psychology, enriching the humanities and even literary studies through an original psychoanalytic reading of the works of Botev and Yavorov.

Stoil Mavrodiev undoubtedly enriched and further developed the subject area of the history of Bulgarian psychology. The author's extensive research and expertise in the difficult field of analytical-interpretive research, proof of which is his study of the scientific work of Lyubomir Rusev and of a number of other Bulgarian psychologists, is commendable. There is no doubt that the book is a valuable read for psychologists and for all specialists in the humanities.